

AN ENHANCED WEIGHTED AREA BIASED EXPONENTIAL SIYA DISTRIBUTION FOR LIFETIME ANALYSIS OF CANCER PATIENTS

Shiny C Raj^{1*}, M Vijayakumar² and Prasanth.C.B³

^{1,2} Department of Statistics, Annamalai University, Annamalai Nagar, Tamil Nadu, India.

³ Department of Statistics, Sree Kerala Varma College, Thrissur, Kerala, India

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Abstract:

In this paper, we introduce a novel model called the Area Biased Exponentiated Siya Distribution (WABESD) which is the generalization of the Exponentiated Siya distribution (ESD) through an area biased transformation approach. We thoroughly explore the probability density function (PDF) and the cumulative distribution function (CDF) of the WABESD distribution. Additionally, we investigate the distinctive structural properties of the proposed model, including the survival function, hazard function, reverse hazard function, harmonic mean, moments, moment generating function (MGF), characteristic function (CF), entropy measures, and Bonferroni and Lorenz curves. The model parameters are estimated using the maximum likelihood estimation method. Finally test the performance of the distribution model using a survival data.

Keywords:—Area biased, Exponentiated distribution. Maximum likelihood function, Incomplete gamma function, moments, goodness of fit

Introduction:

Weighted distributions play a crucial role in statistical modeling, especially when dealing with situations where there is a bias toward events in terms of their occurrence probability due to the sampling process. These models were developed by Fisher [1], who used them to describe the ascertainment biases. Later Rao [2] presented a unified theory of the application of these distributions to solve problems where events do not occur randomly but in non-experimental, non-replicated, and non-random situations. One case that can be considered is the area-biased sampling approach, commonly used in ecology, environment, and survival analysis where the bigger units are likely to get selected more often. In this study, we develop a weighted distribution based on the area-biased version of the three-parameter Exponentiated Siya distribution. The Siya distribution is one of the new models in statistics designed to handle skewed lifetime data [3]. Its power form, in turn, introduces flexibility and makes it possible to fit a wide range of shapes for the hazard functions and tail behaviors. Therefore, introducing an area-biased weight function transforms the 3P-ES distribution into an area-biased version of this model, assigning more weights to bigger numbers. Thus, we create the area-biased generalized exponentiated Siya distribution.

Several useful works have been done by various scholars on developing some probability distributions with weights along with their statistical properties and applications in several disciplines. Some such examples include: Rama Shankar [4] proposed a size-biased Poisson-Akash distribution and explained their applications. Mashael A A et al. [5] developed a modified Gamma distribution and analyzed its estimation and various applications. Rashid Qaisar et al. [6] constructed a 3-parameter Quasi gamma distribution and examined its properties. G Tzavelas et al. [7] introduced a size-biased Frechet distribution and studied their properties and statistical inference. Arunkumar Rao et al. [8] introduced the estimation of parameters of an area-biased Rayleigh distribution. R B Ade et al. [9] characterized and estimated area-biased Quasi Akash distribution. Jaimole V M et al. [10] proposed a unique area-biased 2-parameter Pranav distribution with their medical applications. Afaq Ahmad et al. [11] studied a weighted Lomax distribution and explained their properties. Eric U et al. [12] studied the properties and application of Gamma distribution. Asgar Ali et al. [13] provided a review of a new area biased distribution with its essential properties. Abdullah Hardhan et al. [14] studied an area biased one parameter exponential distribution. Nuri Celik [15] provided some application of Area biased distribution.

1. Weighted Area Biased Exponential Siya Distribution (WABESD)

1.1. The probability density function (pdf)

The Exponential Siya distribution is given by

$$f(x, \alpha, \beta, \theta) = \frac{\beta x^{(\alpha-1)} e^{(-\frac{x}{\theta})^\beta}}{\theta^\alpha \Gamma(\frac{\alpha}{\beta})} \quad x > 0, \alpha, \beta, \theta > 0$$

α, θ are scale parameter and β is the shape parameter

(1)

and its cumulative distribution function is $F(x) = \frac{\Gamma(\frac{\alpha}{\beta}, (\frac{x}{\theta})^\beta)}{\Gamma(\frac{\alpha}{\beta})}$

(2)

Where $\Gamma(\frac{\alpha}{\beta}, (\frac{x}{\theta})^\beta)$ is an incomplete gamma function.

Its mean, variance and r^{th} raw moments are respectively

$$E(x) = \frac{\theta(\alpha+1)}{\beta}$$

(3)

$$E(x^2) = \theta^2 \frac{\Gamma(\alpha+2)/\beta}{\Gamma(\alpha/\beta)}$$

(4)

$$E(x^r) = \theta^r \frac{\Gamma(\frac{\alpha+r}{\beta})}{\Gamma(\frac{\alpha}{\beta})}$$

(5)

Suppose X is a non-negative random variable with probability density function $f(x)$. Let $w(x)$ be the non-negative weight function, then the probability density function of the weighted random variable X is given by

$$f(x) = \frac{w(x)f(x)}{E[w(x)]} \quad : \quad x > 0$$

(6)

Where $w(x)$ be the non negative weight function and $E(w(x)) = \int w(x) f(x) dx < \alpha$.

In this paper we are discussing a weighted version of Exponential Siya distribution named weighted area biased Exponential Siya Distribution by putting the weight function.

$w(x) = x^c$; Where $c = 2$ then (6) becomes

$$f(x) = \frac{x^2 f(x)}{E(x^2)}$$

the resultant model is called

Weighted area biased exponential Siya Distribution(WABESD)

Where $E(x^2) = \int_0^\infty x^2 f(x, \alpha, \beta, \theta) dx = \int_0^\infty x^2 \frac{\beta x^{(\alpha-1)} e^{(-\frac{x}{\theta})^\beta}}{\theta^\alpha \Gamma(\frac{\alpha}{\beta})} dx = \theta^2 \frac{\Gamma(\alpha+2)/\beta}{\Gamma(\alpha/\beta)}$

So (7) will be $f(x, \alpha, \beta, \theta) = \frac{x^2 \frac{\beta x^{(\alpha-1)} e^{(-\frac{x}{\theta})^\beta}}{\theta^\alpha \Gamma(\frac{\alpha}{\beta})}}{\theta^2 \frac{\Gamma(\alpha+2)/\beta}{\Gamma(\alpha/\beta)}} = \frac{\beta x^{\alpha+1} e^{(-\frac{x}{\theta})^\beta}}{\theta^{\alpha+2} \Gamma(\frac{\alpha+2}{\beta})}$

$$f(x, \alpha, \beta, \theta) = \frac{\beta x^{\alpha+1} e^{(-\frac{x}{\theta})^\beta}}{\theta^{\alpha+2} \Gamma(\frac{\alpha+2}{\beta})} ; \quad 0 \leq X < \infty ; \quad \alpha, \beta, \theta > 0$$

(8)

Which is the pdf of weighted area biased exponential Siya distribution.

1.2 .Cumulative Distribution Function (cdf) .

The cdf $F(x)$ of a continuous random variable X is defined as the probability that X takes on a value less than or equal to x .

$$F(x) = P(X \leq x) = \int_0^x f(x, \alpha, \beta, \theta) dx$$

$$F(t) = \int_0^t \frac{\beta t^{\alpha+1} e^{(-\frac{t}{\theta})^\beta}}{\theta^{\alpha+2} \Gamma(\frac{\alpha+2}{\beta})} dx = \frac{\beta}{\theta^{\alpha+2} \Gamma(\frac{\alpha+2}{\beta})} \int_0^t t^{\alpha+1} e^{(-\frac{t}{\theta})^\beta} dt$$

Put $u = (\frac{t}{\theta})^\beta$ then $t = \theta u^{1/\beta}$ and $dt = \frac{\theta}{\beta} u^{\frac{1-\beta}{\beta}} du$

And the limits of the integration changes to when $t=0, u = (\frac{0}{\theta})^\beta = 0$

When $t = x, u = (\frac{x}{\theta})^\beta$ substituting this into the above integral

$$F(t) = \frac{\beta}{\theta^{\alpha+2} \Gamma(\frac{\alpha+2}{\beta})} \int_0^{(\frac{x}{\theta})^\beta} (\theta u^{1/\beta})^{\alpha+1} e^{-u} \frac{\theta}{\beta} u^{\frac{1-\beta}{\beta}} du \text{ simplify}$$

$$F(t) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\frac{\alpha+2}{\beta})} \int_0^{\left(\frac{x}{\theta}\right)^\beta} e^{-u} u^{\frac{\alpha+2-\beta}{\beta}} du = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\frac{\alpha+2}{\beta})} \int_0^{\left(\frac{x}{\theta}\right)^\beta} e^{-u} u^{\frac{\alpha+2}{\beta}-1} du$$

$$F(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\frac{\alpha+2}{\beta})} \gamma\left[\frac{\alpha+2}{\beta}, \left(\frac{x}{\theta}\right)^\beta\right] \tag{9}$$

It is a lower incomplete gamma function.

Fig 1: PDF & CDF Plot of Weighted area biased Exponential Siya Distribution

2. Reliability Measures.

2.1. Reliability Function.

Reliability function refers to the probability that the system works for more than a given period of time. The reliability function is also called the survival or survivor function. Reliability function can be derived from the complement of the cumulative distribution function of the distribution under consideration. In cases where the reliability analysis is being considered, the letter ‘t’ denotes time. The reliability function for the WABES Model is derived as follows:

$$R(t) = P(T > t) = 1 - F(t)$$

$$R(t; \alpha, \beta, \theta) = 1 - F(x; \alpha, \beta, \theta)$$

$$R(t; \alpha, \beta, \theta) = 1 - \frac{1}{\Gamma(\frac{\alpha+2}{\beta})} \gamma\left[\frac{\alpha+2}{\beta}, \left(\frac{x}{\theta}\right)^\beta\right]$$

$$R(t; \alpha, \beta, \theta) = \frac{\Gamma(\frac{\alpha+2}{\beta}) - \gamma\left[\frac{\alpha+2}{\beta}, \left(\frac{x}{\theta}\right)^\beta\right]}{\Gamma(\frac{\alpha+2}{\beta})} ; t > 0$$

(10)

2.2. Hazard function.

The hazard function is also known as the failure rate function is the instantaneous rate of failure at time t, given that the system has survived up to time t. it is defined as

$$h(t) = \frac{f(t)}{R(t)}$$

$$h(t) = \frac{\frac{\beta x^{\alpha+1} e^{-\left(\frac{x}{\theta}\right)^\beta}}{\theta^{\alpha+2} \Gamma(\frac{\alpha+2}{\beta})}}{\frac{\Gamma(\frac{\alpha+2}{\beta}) - \gamma\left[\frac{\alpha+2}{\beta}, \left(\frac{x}{\theta}\right)^\beta\right]}{\Gamma(\frac{\alpha+2}{\beta})}}$$

$$h(t) = \left(\frac{\beta x^{\alpha+1} e^{-\left(\frac{x}{\theta}\right)^\beta}}{\theta^{\alpha+2} (\Gamma(\frac{\alpha+2}{\beta}) - \gamma\left[\frac{\alpha+2}{\beta}, \left(\frac{x}{\theta}\right)^\beta\right])} \right)$$

(11)

2.3 . Reverse hazard function.

The reverse hazard function or backward recurrence time rate is defined as the conditional probability of failure in the immediate past, given that failure has occurred by time t. it is given by

$$h_r(t) = \frac{f(t)}{F(t)}$$

$$h_r(t) = \frac{\frac{\beta t^{\alpha+1} e^{-\left(\frac{t}{\theta}\right)^\beta}}{\theta^{\alpha+2} \Gamma(\frac{\alpha+2}{\beta})}}{\frac{1}{\Gamma(\frac{\alpha+2}{\beta})} \gamma\left[\frac{\alpha+2}{\beta}, \left(\frac{t}{\theta}\right)^\beta\right]} ; t \geq 0$$

after simplification

$$h_r(t) = \left(\frac{\beta x^{\alpha+1} e^{-\left(\frac{t}{\theta}\right)^\beta}}{\theta^{\alpha+2} \Gamma\left(\frac{\alpha+2}{\beta}\right) \left(\frac{t}{\theta}\right)^\beta} \right); t \geq 0 \tag{12}$$

2.4. Mills Ratio.

The Mills ratio as the ratio of the survival function to the probability density function of a random variable. It is widely used in statistics to analyse the tail behavior.

For a continuous random variable with pdf $f(x)$ and cdf $F(X)$, the Mills ratio M.R is

$$\begin{aligned} \text{M.R} &= \frac{R(x)}{f(x)} = \frac{1-F(x)}{f(x)} \\ \text{M.R} &= \frac{\Gamma\left(\frac{\alpha+2}{\beta}\right) - \Gamma\left(\frac{\alpha+2}{\beta}, \left(\frac{x}{\theta}\right)^\beta\right)}{\Gamma\left(\frac{\alpha+2}{\beta}\right)} \text{ by simplification} \\ \text{M.R} &= \frac{\beta x^{\alpha+1} e^{-\left(\frac{x}{\theta}\right)^\beta}}{\theta^{\alpha+2} \Gamma\left(\frac{\alpha+2}{\beta}\right)} \\ \text{M.R} &= \left(\frac{\theta^{\alpha+2} \left[\Gamma\left(\frac{\alpha+2}{\beta}\right) - \Gamma\left(\frac{\alpha+2}{\beta}, \left(\frac{x}{\theta}\right)^\beta \right) \right]}{\beta x^{\alpha+1} e^{-\left(\frac{x}{\theta}\right)^\beta}} \right) \end{aligned}$$

(13)

Fig 2: plots of Reliability and Hazard function.

3. Moments and related measures

In this section we obtain different statistical properties of area biased exponentiated Siya Distribution. Especially moments, harmonic mean, moment generating function and characteristics function.

3.1. Moments.

Let X be a random variable following weighted area biased exponential siya distribution with parameters α, β , and θ . Then the r^{th} order raw moments $E(x^r)$ is obtained as $E(x^r) = \mu'_r = \int_0^\infty x^r f(x, \alpha, \beta, \theta) dx$

$$E(x^r) = \int_0^\infty x^r \frac{\beta x^{\alpha+1} e^{-\left(\frac{x}{\theta}\right)^\beta}}{\theta^{\alpha+2} \Gamma\left(\frac{\alpha+2}{\beta}\right)} dx = \frac{\beta}{\theta^{\alpha+2} \Gamma\left(\frac{\alpha+2}{\beta}\right)} \int_0^\infty x^{\alpha+r+1} e^{-\left(\frac{x}{\theta}\right)^\beta} dx$$

Using the substitution $u = \left(\frac{x}{\theta}\right)^\beta$. we found that

$$E(x^r) = \frac{\beta}{\theta^{\alpha+2} \Gamma\left(\frac{\alpha+2}{\beta}\right)} \frac{\theta^{\alpha+r+2}}{\beta} \Gamma\left(\frac{\alpha+r+2}{\beta}\right)$$

$$E(x^r) = \theta^r \frac{\Gamma\left(\frac{\alpha+r+2}{\beta}\right)}{\Gamma\left(\frac{\alpha+2}{\beta}\right)}$$

(14)

Now substituting $r=1, 2$ and 3 we get the first three moments of the WABES distribution

$$\text{Mean } E(x) = \mu'_1 = \theta \frac{\Gamma\left(\frac{\alpha+3}{\beta}\right)}{\Gamma\left(\frac{\alpha+2}{\beta}\right)} ; E(x^2) = \mu'_2 = \theta^2 \frac{\Gamma\left(\frac{\alpha+4}{\beta}\right)}{\Gamma\left(\frac{\alpha+2}{\beta}\right)} ; E(x^3) = \theta^3 \frac{\Gamma\left(\frac{\alpha+5}{\beta}\right)}{\Gamma\left(\frac{\alpha+2}{\beta}\right)} \text{ etc} \tag{15}$$

$$\text{So variance } V(X) = \mu'_2 - (\mu'_1)^2 = \theta^2 \frac{\Gamma\left(\frac{\alpha+4}{\beta}\right)}{\Gamma\left(\frac{\alpha+2}{\beta}\right)} - \left(\theta \frac{\Gamma\left(\frac{\alpha+3}{\beta}\right)}{\Gamma\left(\frac{\alpha+2}{\beta}\right)} \right)^2$$

$$V(X) = \theta^2 \left(\frac{\Gamma(\frac{\alpha+4}{\beta})\Gamma(\frac{\alpha+2}{\beta}) - \Gamma(\frac{\alpha+3}{\beta})^2}{\Gamma(\frac{\alpha+2}{\beta})^2} \right)$$

(16)

3.2. Harmonic mean.

The Harmonic mean is the reciprocal of the arithmetic mean of the reciprocals. The Harmonic mean of the proposed area biased exponential Siya Distribution is obtained by

$$H.M = \left(E\left[\frac{1}{X}\right] \right)^{-1}$$

So first find $E\left(\frac{1}{x}\right) = \int_0^\infty \frac{1}{x} f(x, \alpha, \beta, \theta) dx$

$$E\left(\frac{1}{x}\right) = \int_0^\infty \frac{1}{x} \frac{\beta x^{\alpha+1} e^{-\left(\frac{x}{\theta}\right)^\beta}}{\theta^{\alpha+2} \Gamma\left(\frac{\alpha+2}{\beta}\right)} dx = \int_0^\infty \frac{\beta x^\alpha e^{-\left(\frac{x}{\theta}\right)^\beta}}{\theta^{\alpha+2} \Gamma\left(\frac{\alpha+2}{\beta}\right)} dx$$

$E\left(\frac{1}{x}\right) = \frac{\beta}{\theta^{\alpha+2} \Gamma\left(\frac{\alpha+2}{\beta}\right)} \int_0^\infty x^\alpha e^{-\left(\frac{x}{\theta}\right)^\beta} dx$. We use the substitution $u = \left(\frac{x}{\theta}\right)^\beta$ and simplify we get the result as

$$= \frac{\beta}{\theta^{\alpha+2} \Gamma\left(\frac{\alpha+2}{\beta}\right)} \frac{\theta^{\alpha+1}}{\beta} \int_0^\infty e^{-u} u^{\frac{\alpha+1-\beta}{\beta}} du$$

$$E\left(\frac{1}{x}\right) = \frac{\beta}{\theta^{\alpha+2} \Gamma\left(\frac{\alpha+2}{\beta}\right)} \frac{\theta^{\alpha+1}}{\beta} \Gamma\left(\frac{\alpha+1}{\beta}\right) = \frac{\Gamma\left(\frac{\alpha+1}{\beta}\right)}{\theta \Gamma\left(\frac{\alpha+2}{\beta}\right)}$$

$$H.M = \frac{\theta \Gamma\left(\frac{\alpha+2}{\beta}\right)}{\Gamma\left(\frac{\alpha+1}{\beta}\right)}$$

(17)

3.3. Moment Generating Function and Characteristic function.

Let X be the random variable following the weighted area biased exponential Siya distribution with parameters $\alpha, \beta,$ and θ . Then the moment generating function of this distribution is obtained as

$$M_x(t) = E(e^{tx}) = \int_0^\infty e^{tx} f(x, \alpha, \beta, \theta) dx,$$

$$M_x(t) = \int_0^\infty e^{tx} \frac{\beta x^{\alpha+1} e^{-\left(\frac{x}{\theta}\right)^\beta}}{\theta^{\alpha+2} \Gamma\left(\frac{\alpha+2}{\beta}\right)} dx = \frac{\beta}{\Gamma\left(\frac{\alpha+2}{\beta}\right) \theta^{\alpha+2}} \int_0^\infty x^{\alpha+1} e^{tx} e^{-\left(\frac{x}{\theta}\right)^\beta} dx$$

The Integrand is quite complex. so using Taylor series expansion

$$e^{tx} = \sum_{n=0}^\infty \frac{(tx)^n}{n!} = 1 + tx + \frac{(tx)^2}{2!} + \frac{(tx)^3}{3!} + \dots$$

Now substitute this into the above integrals the MGF becomes

$$M_x(t) = E[e^{tx}] = \int_0^\infty \left(\sum_{n=0}^\infty \frac{(tx)^n}{n!} \right) f(x, \alpha, \beta, \theta) dx$$

$$M_x(t) = \sum_{n=0}^\infty \frac{t^n}{n!} \int_0^\infty x^n f(x, \alpha, \beta, \theta) dx$$

$$M_x(t) = \sum_{n=0}^\infty \frac{t^n}{n!} E(x^n) \text{ using equ (14)}$$

$$M_x(t) = \sum_{n=0}^\infty \frac{t^n}{n!} \theta^n \frac{\Gamma\left(\frac{\alpha+n+2}{\beta}\right)}{\Gamma\left(\frac{\alpha+2}{\beta}\right)} \text{ ie}$$

$$M_x(t) = \frac{1}{\Gamma\left(\frac{\alpha+2}{\beta}\right)} \sum_{n=0}^\infty \frac{(t\theta)^n}{n!} \Gamma\left(\frac{\alpha+n+2}{\beta}\right) \tag{18}$$

$$\text{And Characteristic function } \phi_X(t) = \frac{1}{\Gamma\left(\frac{\alpha+2}{\beta}\right)} \sum_{n=0}^\infty \frac{(it\theta)^n}{n!} \Gamma\left(\frac{\alpha+n+2}{\beta}\right) \tag{19}$$

4. Entropy measures

Entropy is utilized in various fields under probability and statistics. Entropy is a measure that represents the level of uncertainty and chaos in a system, and thus is said to be the measure of disorder. Entropy of random variable X is the measure of variance in uncertainty.

4.1. Renyi Entropy ($H_q(X)$)

The Renyi Entropy of order q where $q=0,1$. For a continuous distribution with pdf f(x) is defined as

$$H_q(x) = \frac{1}{1-q} \ln \left(\int_0^\infty [f(x)]^q dx \right) \tag{20}$$

$$\text{Let us consider } \int_0^\infty [f(x)]^q dx = \int_0^\infty \left(\frac{\beta x^{\alpha+1} e^{-\left(\frac{x}{\theta}\right)^\beta}}{\theta^{\alpha+2} \Gamma\left(\frac{\alpha+2}{\beta}\right)} \right)^q dx = \int_0^\infty \frac{\beta^q x^{q(\alpha+1)}}{\theta^{q(\alpha+2)} [\Gamma\left(\frac{\alpha+2}{\beta}\right)]^q} e^{q\left(-\frac{x}{\theta}\right)^\beta} dx$$

(A)

For evaluating the integral put $u=q(\frac{x}{\theta})^\beta$ so $x=\theta(\frac{u}{q})^{1/\beta}$ and $dx = \frac{\theta}{\beta} q^{-1/\beta} u^{\frac{1}{\beta}-1} du$

When $x=0, u=0$ and when $x \rightarrow \infty, u \rightarrow \infty$

$$\int_0^\infty [f(x)]^q dx = \frac{\beta^q}{\theta^{q(\alpha+2)} [\Gamma(\frac{\alpha+2}{\beta})]^q} \frac{\theta^{q(\alpha+1)+1}}{\beta q} \int_0^\infty e^{-u} u^{\frac{q(\alpha+1)+1-\beta}{\beta}} du$$

$$\int_0^\infty [f(x)]^q dx = \frac{\beta^{(q-1)\theta^{(1-q)}}}{q \frac{\theta^{(\alpha+1)+1}}{\beta}} \frac{\Gamma(\frac{q(\alpha+1)+1}{\beta})}{[\Gamma(\frac{\alpha+2}{\beta})]^q}; \text{ finally the Renyi Entropy equ (20) becomes}$$

$$H_q(x) = \frac{1}{1-q} \left[(q-1) \ln(\beta) + (1-q) \ln(\theta) - \frac{q(\alpha+1)+1}{\beta} \ln(q) + \ln(\Gamma(\frac{q(\alpha+1)+1}{\beta})) - q \ln(\Gamma(\frac{\alpha+2}{\beta})) \right]$$

4.2. Tsallis Entropy (S_r(X))

The Tsallis entropy of order r where r>0 and r≠1 for a continuous random variable with pdf f(x) is defined as

$S_r(X) = \frac{1}{r-1} (\int_0^\infty [f(x)]^r dx - 1)$ so with reference to Renyi entropy the Tsallis Entropy becomes

$$S_r(X) = \frac{1}{r-1} \left(\frac{\beta^{(r-1)\theta^{(1-r)}}}{r \frac{\theta^{(\alpha+1)+1}}{\beta}} \frac{\Gamma(\frac{r(\alpha+1)+1}{\beta})}{[\Gamma(\frac{\alpha+2}{\beta})]^r} - 1 \right) \tag{21}$$

5. Order Statistics.

Let $X_{(1)}, X_{(2)}, \dots, X_{(n)}$ be the order statistics of a random sample X_1, X_2, \dots, X_n drawn from the continuous population with probability density function $f(x; \alpha, \beta, \theta)$ and cumulative density function with $F(x; \alpha, \beta, \theta)$, The kth order statistics $X_{(k)}$ of a random sample of size n from the WABES distribution provide information on the distribution of kth sample value.

For a sample of size n, the pdf of the kth order statistics $X_{(k)}$ is

$$f_{X_{(k)}}(x) = \frac{n!}{(k-1)!(n-k)!} f(x) [F(x)]^{(k-1)} [1-F(x)]^{(n-k)} \quad ; k = 1, 2, 3, \dots$$

Using (8) and (9) the probability density function of the kth order statistics of weighted area biased exponential Siya distribution is given by

$$f_{X_{(k)}}(x) = \frac{n!}{(k-1)!(n-k)!} \frac{\beta x^{\alpha+1} e^{-(\frac{x}{\theta})^\beta}}{\theta^{\alpha+2} \Gamma(\frac{\alpha+2}{\beta})} \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\frac{\alpha+2}{\beta})} \Gamma\left[\frac{\alpha+2}{\beta}, \left(\frac{x}{\theta}\right)^\beta\right] \right)^{(k-1)} \left[1 - \frac{1}{\Gamma(\frac{\alpha+2}{\beta})} \Gamma\left[\frac{\alpha+2}{\beta}, \left(\frac{x}{\theta}\right)^\beta\right] \right]^{(n-k)}$$

Put k=1 the pdf of first order $X_{(1)}$ is given by

$$f_{X_{(1)}}(x) = \frac{n \beta x^{\alpha+1} e^{-(\frac{x}{\theta})^\beta}}{\theta^{\alpha+2} \Gamma(\frac{\alpha+2}{\beta})} \left[1 - \frac{1}{\Gamma(\frac{\alpha+2}{\beta})} \Gamma\left[\frac{\alpha+2}{\beta}, \left(\frac{x}{\theta}\right)^\beta\right] \right]^{(n-1)} \tag{23}$$

Put k = n, the pdf of nth order $X_{(n)}$ is given by

$$f_{X_{(n)}}(x) = \frac{n \beta x^{\alpha+1} e^{-(\frac{x}{\theta})^\beta}}{\theta^{\alpha+2} \Gamma(\frac{\alpha+2}{\beta})} \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\frac{\alpha+2}{\beta})} \Gamma\left[\frac{\alpha+2}{\beta}, \left(\frac{x}{\theta}\right)^\beta\right] \right)^{(k-1)} \tag{24}$$

6 Method of Maximum Likelihood Estimation (MLE).

Maximum likelihood estimation method has been most widely used method for estimating the parameters of the weighted distribution. Let x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n be a random sample from an WABESD. Then the corresponding likelihood function $L(\alpha, \beta, \theta/x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)$ is given by the product of the pdf evaluated at each observation.

$$L(\alpha, \beta, \theta/x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) = \prod_{i=1}^n \frac{\beta x_i^{\alpha+1} e^{-(\frac{x_i}{\theta})^\beta}}{\theta^{\alpha+2} \Gamma(\frac{\alpha+2}{\beta})}$$

The log likelihood function is given by

$$\text{Log } L = \sum_{i=1}^n [\ln(\beta) + (\alpha + 1) \ln(x_i) - (\alpha + 2) \ln(\theta) - \ln(\Gamma(\frac{\alpha+2}{\beta})) - \left(\frac{x_i}{\theta}\right)^\beta]$$

$$\log L = n \ln(\beta) + \sum_{i=1}^n (\alpha + 1) \ln(x_i) - n(\alpha + 2) \ln(\theta) - n \ln\left(\Gamma\left(\frac{\alpha+2}{\beta}\right)\right) - \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{x_i}{\theta}\right)^\beta$$

(25)

To find the MLE $(\hat{\alpha}, \hat{\beta}, \hat{\theta})$, we need to take the partial derivatives of log L with respect to α, β, θ , set them to zero, and solve the resulting system of equations.

The partial derivatives are

$$\frac{\partial \log L}{\partial \alpha} = \sum_{i=1}^n \ln(x_i) - \frac{n}{\beta} \frac{\Gamma'(\frac{\alpha+2}{\beta})}{\Gamma(\frac{\alpha+2}{\beta})} = 0$$

$$= \sum_{i=1}^n \ln(x_i) - \frac{n}{\beta} \Psi\left(\frac{\alpha+2}{\beta}\right) = 0; \text{ where } \Psi(Z) = \frac{\Gamma'(Z)}{\Gamma(Z)} \text{ is the di gamma function}$$

ie $\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \ln x_i = \frac{1}{\beta} \Psi\left(\frac{\alpha+2}{\beta}\right)$ (26)

$$\frac{\partial \log L}{\partial \beta} = \frac{n}{\beta} + \frac{n(\alpha+2)}{\beta^2} \Psi\left(\frac{\alpha+2}{\beta}\right) - \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{x_i}{\theta}\right)^\beta \ln\left(\frac{x_i}{\theta}\right) = 0$$

$$= -n \left(\frac{\alpha+2}{\theta}\right) + \frac{\beta}{\theta^{\beta+1}} \sum_{i=1}^n x_i^\beta = 0$$

(27)

(28)

It is vital to note that the preceding system of nonlinear equations has an analytical solution that is too complex to be solved algebraically. So we predict the suggested distribution's parameter using R and Wolfram Mathematica.

And the second order partial derivatives of log L with respect to these parameters are

$$\frac{\partial^2 \log L}{\partial \alpha^2} = -\frac{n}{\beta^2} \Psi'\left(\frac{\alpha+2}{\beta}\right); \quad \Psi'(Z) \text{ is the tri gamma function.}$$

$$\frac{\partial^2 \log L}{\partial \beta^2} = -\frac{n}{\beta^2} - \frac{2n(\alpha+2)}{\beta^3} \Psi\left(\frac{\alpha+2}{\beta}\right) - \frac{n(\alpha+2)}{\beta^3} \Psi'\left(\frac{\alpha+2}{\beta}\right) - \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{x_i}{\theta}\right)^\beta \left(\ln\left(\frac{x_i}{\theta}\right)\right)^2$$

$$\frac{\partial^2 \log L}{\partial \theta^2} = \frac{n(\alpha+2)}{\theta^2} - \frac{\beta(\beta+1)}{\theta^{\beta+2}} \sum_{i=1}^n x_i^\beta$$

$$\frac{\partial^2 \log L}{\partial \alpha \partial \beta} = n \left[\frac{1}{\beta^2} \Psi\left(\frac{\alpha+2}{\beta}\right) + \frac{n(\alpha+2)}{\beta^3} \Psi'\left(\frac{\alpha+2}{\beta}\right) \right]$$

$$\frac{\partial^2 \log L}{\partial \alpha \partial \theta} = \frac{n}{\theta}$$

$$\frac{\partial^2 \log L}{\partial \theta \partial \beta} = -\frac{1}{\theta^{\beta+1}} \sum_{i=1}^n x_i^\beta (1 + \beta \ln\left(\frac{x_i}{\theta}\right))$$

7. Likelihood Ratio Test

Let X_1, X_2, \dots, X_n be a random sample from a Weighted area biased exponentiated Siya Distribution or exponential Siya distribution. To examine its significance we consider the test hypothesis is

$$H_0: f(x) = f(x, \alpha, \beta, \theta) \quad \text{against} \quad H_1: f(x) = f_a(x, \alpha, \beta, \theta)$$

To determine whether the random sample of size n come from the exponentiated Siya distribution or weighted area biased exponential Siya distribution, the test statistics used is

$$\Delta = \frac{L_1}{L_0} = \prod_{i=1}^n \frac{f_a(x_i, \alpha, \beta, \theta)}{f(x_i, \alpha, \beta, \theta)}$$

$$\Delta = \prod_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{\beta x_i^\alpha e^{-\frac{x_i}{\theta}^\beta}}{\theta^{(\alpha+1)} \Gamma\left(\frac{\alpha+1}{\beta}\right)} \right) \left(\frac{\beta x_i^{(\alpha-1)} e^{-\frac{x_i}{\theta}^\beta}}{\theta^\alpha \Gamma\left(\frac{\alpha}{\beta}\right)} \right)$$

$$\Delta = \frac{\Gamma(\frac{\alpha}{\beta})}{\theta \Gamma(\frac{\alpha+1}{\beta})} \prod_{i=1}^n x_i. \quad \text{We reject the null hypothesis if}$$

$$\frac{\Gamma(\frac{\alpha}{\beta})}{\theta \Gamma(\frac{\alpha+1}{\beta})} \prod_{i=1}^n x_i > k \text{ or } \prod_{i=1}^n x_i > k \frac{\theta \Gamma(\frac{\alpha+1}{\beta})}{\Gamma(\frac{\alpha}{\beta})}$$

For large sample size n , $2 \log L$ is distributed as chi-square distribution with one degree of freedom and also p-value is obtained from the chi-square distribution.

8. Application

In this section, a practical data set is considered in order to show that the suggested distribution gives a better fit compared with two other different distributions. We use R software for doing numerical calculations on datasets, estimating unknown parameters, and calculating model selection criteria. In order to compare the Weighted Area-Biased Exponential Siya Distribution (WABESD) with the Size-Biased Fréchet Distribution (SBFD)[7] and the Length-Biased Weighted Lomax Distribution (LBWLD[11]), the following values will be taken into consideration: AIC (Akaike Information Criterion), AICC (Corrected Akaike Information Criterion), and BIC (Bayesian Information Criterion).

The formulas for calculation of AIC, AICC and BIC values are

$$AIC = 2k - 2 \log L, \quad AICC = AIC + \frac{2k(k+1)}{n-k-1} \quad \text{and} \quad BIC = k \log n - 2 \log L$$

Where k is the number of parameters in the statistical model, n is the sample size and $-2\log L$ is the maximized value of the log-likelihood function under the considered model.

Data set:

The following dataset(taken from Kaggle data base) consist of 100 breast cancer patients survival time in years.
 1.41,9.03,3.95,2.74,0.51,0.51,0.18,6.03,2.76,3.70,0.06,10.51,5.36,0.72,0.60,0.61,1.09,2.23,1.70,1.03,2.84,0.45,1.03,1.37,1.83,4.62,0.67,2.17,2.69,0.14,2.81,0.56,0.20,8.93,10.11,4.96,1.09,0.31,3.46,1.74,0.39,2.05,0.11,7.20,0.90,3.26,1.12,2.20,2.38,0.62,1.048,4.48,8.42,6.76,2.73,7.65,0.28,0.66,0.14,1.18,1.48,0.95,5.29,1.33,0.99,2.35,0.46,4.86,0.23,13.00,4.44,0.67,0.02,5.07,3.68,3.92,4.43,0.23,1.33,0.37,5.97,2.93,1.21,0.20,1.12,1.18,3.93,3.04,6.55,1.92,0.38,3.75,4.29,2.48,4.43,2.04,2.23,1.68,0.08,0.34.

Table1. Analytical result for the dataset

Models	MLE	S.E	-2logL	AIC	BIC	AICc
WABESD	$\alpha=0.002207$ $\beta=0.37018$ $\theta = 0.02043$ 6	$\alpha=0.310836$ $\beta=0.052015$ $\theta = 0.02695$	405.4693	411.4693	419.2848	411.7193
LBWLD	$\theta = 2.95839$ $\lambda = 1.55042$	$\theta = 0.5403381$ $\lambda = 0.592695$	416.6411	420.6411	425.8515	420.7648
SBFD	$\delta = 0.75119$ 5 $\beta=0.67874$	$\delta = 0.11775$ $\beta=0.04593$	449.4134	453.4134	458.6238	453.5371

From the above table WABESD has lesser AIC, BIC, AICC values as compared to LBWLD and SBFD. Hence we conclude that WABESD has a better fit than other two distributions.

9. Conclusion.

In this study, the Exponentiated Siya Distribution is extended into a new distribution known as the Weighted Area-Biased Exponential Siya Distribution. The distribution is generated using weighted techniques, and the estimation of the distribution's parameters is done using the Maximum Likelihood Estimator method. Some mathematical properties are considered, alongside reliability functions. To conclude, a practical data set is used to evaluate the model's goodness-of-fit performance.

Conflict of Interest:

The authors confirm that there are no conflicts of interest related to this work.

Abbreviations.

ESD	Exponentiated Siya Distribution
WABESD	Weighted Area Biased Exponential Siya I Distribution
MLE	Maximum Likelihood Function
S.E	Standard Error
AIC	Akaike Information Criterion
BIC	Bayesian Information Criterion
AICC	Corrected Akaike Information Criterion
LBWLD	Length Biased Weighted Lomax Distribution
SBFD	Size Biased Frechet Distribution

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